

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

РОЛЬ БИОРАЗНООБРАЗИЯ В УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ БИОСФЕРЫ

Асланова Е.Г.

*Азербайджанское государственное аграрное университет
Кандидат сельскохозяйственных наук*

Бабакишиева Т.С.

*Азербайджанское государственное аграрное университет
кандидат биологических наук*

Аббасова Г.Ф.

Азербайджанское государственное аграрное университет

THE ROLE OF BIODIVERSITY IN THE SUSTAINABILITY OF THE BIOSPHERE

Aslanova E.,

*Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
PhD in Agricultural Sciences*

Babakishieva T.,

*Azerbaijan State Agrarian University
phD in biological sciences*

Abbasova G.

Azerbaijan State Agrarian University

Аннотация

Постоянная глобальная убыль видов, конечно, более драматична, чем фраза «изменения в региональном видовом составе». Но даже очень небольшие изменения в здоровье и стабильности видов могут оказать огромное влияние на пищевую сеть. Это влияние проявляется непосредственно на видах, в результате чего происходят прерывания генерации цепочек. Уменьшение биоразнообразия может иметь ужасные последствия. Уменьшение биоразнообразия означает уменьшение услуг экосистемы для нас, что, в свою очередь, представляет собой серьезную угрозу для продовольственной безопасности и человечества.

Abstract

Permanent global species decline is, of course, more dramatic than the phrase "changes in regional species composition." But even very small changes in the health and stability of species can have huge impacts on the food web. This effect manifests itself directly on the species, and as a result, chain generation interruptions occur. A decrease in biodiversity can have dire consequences. A decrease in biodiversity means a decrease in the ecosystem's services to us, which in turn is a major threat to food security and humanity.

Ключевые слова: Биоразнообразие, экосистема, окружающая среда, антропогенный фактор.

Keywords: Biodiversity, ecosystem, environment, anthropogenic factor.

Biodiversity is not only the collection of all ecosystems, species and genetic material. It rather expresses the diversity within and between them. This is different from the term "biological resources", which refers to the material components of ecosystems. Biological resources are real entities (particular species of birds, type of wheat grown in a field, oak trees, etc.), while biological diversity is more an attribute of life (variation of bird species, genetic variation of wheat around the world, types of forests, etc.).{2}

Biodiversity is often understood at three levels:

- species diversity refers to the diversity of different species (plants, animals, fungi and microorganisms), including palm trees, elephants and bacteria.

- genetic diversity corresponds to the diversity of genes in plants, animals, fungi and microorganisms. This happens within species as well as between species. For example, poodles, German shepherds, and golden retrievers are all types of dogs, but they all look different.

- ecosystem diversity tropical or temperate forests, hot and cold deserts, swamps, rivers, mountains, coral reefs, etc. refers to all the different habitations or places that exist as Every ecosystem corresponds to a series of complex relationships between biotic (living) components such as plants and animals, and abiotic (non-living) components including sunlight, air, water, minerals, and nutrients.{3}

Due to the emergence of agriculture at the beginning of the Neolithic period, the influence of man on the biosphere increased many times. From that time, the rapid growth of the population began. Undoubtedly, this process manifested itself as the second technological revolution in the history of human society. Due to this, the class structure was formed in different parts of the world. This class structure still exists in a number of countries. The development of agriculture should be considered as the first anthropogenic factor from the point of view of its impact on the environment. The main effect of this factor was manifested in the change of ecosystems. As a result, most of the planet's forest

cover was first turned into grasslands and then into fields for agricultural crops. For example, in China alone, at the beginning of the Neolithic period, 90% of the entire area was covered by forest, but now this value is only 5%. As a result of such human activity, food products increased rapidly, and as a result, conditions were created for energy collection of mechanical and other types of energy at a great cost. The emergence of agriculture led to the transition of the population to a sedentary lifestyle and thus to the creation and rapid development of settlements. {1}

Everything in the history of the planet has a beginning and an end, and in each era many species have become extinct. However, unlike in the past, this process is taking place at an alarming rate in our time. More than 250,000 plant species have died out in just one century, and Wilson estimates that plant species will decline at the rate of three species per hour (or 27,000 species per year) (Wilson, *The Life of the Variety*, 1992). In the spring of 2012, a multi-year comprehensive study by the prestigious University of Exeter, He declared that the sixth mass extinction process (the fifth mass extinction process resulted in the extinction of the dinosaurs 65 million years ago) is currently taking place on Earth (Sanders, Van Veen, *Indirect commensalism promotes persistence of secondary consumer species*, 2012). However, this disappearance process was different from the past because of it. For the first time, Humanity is in charge. Humans continue to destroy rainforests, build asphalt over land, collect plastics in the oceans, convert vast areas into monocultures, and pollute water and soil with chemicals and fertilizers through industrial agriculture and horticulture. However, not every human activity destroys nature. Low-density farming and fishing respect the fragile balance of the natural world. {4}

Small-scale farmers, pastoralists and fishermen are the last custodians of the land. They have worked with and within their eco-systems for millennia, and have changed as these systems have changed. In such "semi-natural" systems, there is no clear distinction between the concepts of "cultural" and "natural" - for centuries, people have shaped ecosystems and their daily lives encompass the biological diversity around them. Along with wild flora and fauna, many domesticated plants and animal breeds that are bred for milk or meat will disappear. According to FAO, 75% of edible plant species can be considered lost once and for all. In the United States, this number is 95%. Currently, 68% of the calories in our food come from three grains: wheat, rice and maize (FAO, *The State of the World's Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture*, 1996). However, these grains are not based on the thousands of rice varieties cultivated in India and China or the thousands of corn varieties grown in Mexico, but on a few hybrid varieties selected and sold by a few large international companies. Mechanization is the number one enemy of diversity. The basis of industrial agriculture is compatibility and high productivity, in other words the promotion of monocultures. Since the 1950s, agricultural production has gradually shifted to depend on selected species and varieties to meet the needs of

the world market. They have nothing to do with individual areas, on the contrary, these varieties can be produced in many environments, they can resist well to any handling and transport method, and moreover, they have a uniform taste. For example, compared to the thousands of apple varieties selected by farmers, only four commercial varieties account for 90% of the world market. However, these species represent great potential for the future of agricultural systems. In certain areas, aboriginal or locally recognized species are the result of natural or anthropogenic selection. Such "soil races" are not limited to plants and animals - the types of local yeast and bacterial cultures are also important in the production of cheese and yogurt, as well as beer. All these species are well adapted to the environmental conditions of their area and need little help from outside (water, fertilizers or pesticides). {8}

They were stronger and more resistant to environmental stresses than 'standard' soils. For this reason, such soils are key elements of any climate change strategy. Their potential to thrive in their native areas (deserts and mountains) makes these lands an important agricultural resource and an important tool in ensuring food sovereignty. It is no coincidence that these types are often closely related to the culture of the local community (traditions, recipes, knowledge, dialect, etc.). These continuous vital activities provide resources for basic needs. The reason why ecosystems acquire complex, diverse structures and functions is the survival, development, diversification and acquisition of new genetic characteristics of wild species. Plant and animal species whose wild relatives are the basis of agricultural production. {6}

Agricultural potential areas and water resources on Earth are rapidly polluting and depleting. Therefore, wild habitat resources are used to develop cultivars that are resistant to environmental pressures and have high production potential. High-yielding countries are investing in the development of new livestock and seed varieties to ensure that their food sector can cope with future food crises. In this context, biological diversity of countries will constitute a significant strength in terms of genetic resources. It was launched by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). The 1992 World Summit on Sustainable Development recognized that the decline of biological diversity could only be addressed through the international efforts of the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Turkey is also a party to the agreement signed and elected by Law No. 4177. The Convention on Biological Diversity aims at the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of biological diversity and the equitable sharing of benefits from genetic resources.

In the activities of the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources aimed at environmental protection and solving the country's ecological problems, the preservation of biological diversity, especially the protection and study of animal and bird species, has a special place.

The organization and development of specially protected natural areas plays an important role in the

protection and study of wild animals. These areas provide conditions for wild animal species to live in safe conditions, to increase their number naturally in a short period of time, and to restore the population of rare animal species. {9}

It is known that climate change is the main cause of biodiversity loss. Scientists believe that global climate change, together with the spread of alien species and changes in land use, will limit the migration opportunities of some species and accelerate their disappearance. So, in the last 10 years, more than 20 percent of the world's fish have either disappeared, are in danger of disappearing, or can be considered rare. Marine ecosystems are also very sensitive to climate change. Climate changes also leave negative traces in agriculture, create conditions for the spread of pests and diseases, and affect the productivity of plants. In short, climate change threatens biodiversity. As sad as it is, at the beginning of the 21st century, humanity is faced with climate change. Therefore, the current situation requires taking serious measures for the preservation and sustainable use of biodiversity {10}.

References

1. National Strategy and Action Plan for the Protection and Sustainable Use of Biological Diversity in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku city, March 24, 2006.
2. Aliyev C.A., Akbarov Z.I., Mammadov A.T. Biological diversity. Baku, "Elm" publishing house, 2008, 232 p.
3. Akbarov Z.I., Mammadov H.I. Basic research strategies of plant genetic resources. Azerbaijan agricultural science, Baku, No. 1-3, 2003, p. 120-124.
4. Asadov K.S., Mirzayev O.H., Mammadov F.M. Dendrology. "Youth", Baku, 2014, 484 p.
5. Ibrahimov Z.A. The forest is a provider of stability and biological diversity in the biosphere. Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Ganja Regional Scientific Center. News Collection No. 42, Ganja, 2011 – p. 43-49.
6. Mehdiyev A.Sh., Ismayilov A.I. Geographic Information Systems. Baku, "Teacher" publishing house, 2005, 232 p.
7. Mehdiyev A.Sh., Azizov B.M., Mehdiyev C.S. Aerospace monitoring. Baku, "Elm", 2005, 208 p.
8. Venitsianov E.V. и др. Ecological monitoring: step by step. M. 2003, 253 p.
9. <https://science.gov.az/>
10. eco.gov.az